

A comparative study of physical blending and hydrogel-derived approaches for Si-based anode materials in Li-ion batteries

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Abstract

Silicon nanomaterials are promising anode materials for lithium-ion batteries (LIB) due to their high theoretical capacity. However, their practical application is hindered by poor electrical conductivity and large volume expansion during cycling. Among these nanomaterials, silicon nanocrystals (SiNC) offer tunable particle size and surface properties that strongly influence electrochemical performance. This study investigates how anode fabrication method and SiNC structural characteristics, including particle size and surface oxidation, affect LIB behavior. Two widely used preparation strategies were compared: (i) physical blending of SiNC with a polyacrylic acid binder and Super P conductive carbon, and (ii) hydrogel-assisted synthesis via in situ polymerization of polypyrrole (PPy) in the presence of phytic acid and SiNC, forming a three-dimensional, flexible, and conductive network. Microstructural analysis, galvanostatic cycling, cyclic voltammetry, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and post-mortem characterization revealed complementary strengths and limitations of each preparation method. Smaller SiNC improved capacity retention in both systems, with a more pronounced effect in hydrogel-derived anodes (44% retention after 500 cycles) due to enhanced dispersion and mechanical support. Super P/SiNC anodes exhibited higher initial discharge capacity (2581 mAh/g), reflecting enhanced lithiation kinetics, whereas PPy/SiNC anodes demonstrated superior long-term cycling stability by mitigating anode degradation. These results highlight the critical interplay between nanomaterial design and electrode architecture and provide mechanistic insight and guidance for the development of next-generation high-performance Si-based anodes.

Keywords

Silicon nanoparticles; silicon-based anodes; physical blending; hydrogel-assisted synthesis; lithium-ion batteries; electrochemical performance

1 Introduction

Nowadays research on Si-based anodes for Li-ion batteries (LIB) focuses on developing anode preparation strategies to harness the exceptionally high theoretical specific capacity of Si (~3579 mAh/g), and to address the barriers to its commercialization, namely, poor electrical conductivity of Si and its significant volume expansion (~300 %) during lithiation and delithiation cycles [1, 2]. These preparation strategies encompass several approaches helping to overcome the Si limitations: (i) nanostructuring (e.g., nanoparticles, nanowires) [3, 4] helping to mitigate the volume expansion and improve the cycling stability [5], (ii) incorporation of electrically conductive components (e.g., carbonaceous materials [6-10], carbon coatings on Si [7, 11], or inorganic compounds [12, 13]) enhancing the material conductivity, and (iii) addition of binders (insulating polymer binders as polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), poly(acrylic acid) (PAA), carboxymethyl cellulose, or alginate [14], or electrically conductive polymers (ECP) such as polyaniline (PANI), polypyrrole (PPy), and poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) [15, 16]) improving the material stability and maintaining particle cohesion.

Based on this, two primary preparation methods of Si-based anode materials have been extensively studied, namely, physical blending and hydrogel-assisted synthesis. Each method offers distinct advantages, but also presents specific challenges. Physical blending method is favored for its simplicity and efficiency, as it involves minimal processing steps: physical mixing of Si material with a conductive additive and a binder, followed by solvent addition and casting onto a current collector [2, 17-19]. However, physically blended composites often exhibit a relatively random distribution of components, which may not guarantee a continuous electron transport pathway throughout the cycling process [20]. This approach is often connected also with increased susceptibility to component disintegration as a result of combining hydrophobic Si and an additive with a hydrophilic binder, and subsequent compromised material cohesion [21].

In contrast, the hydrogel-assisted synthesis method involves a more complex fabrication process. Typically, it includes a pre-synthesis component mixing with subsequent in-situ polymerization of an ECP in the presence of Si, resulting in a composite consisting of Si particles coated with a thin ECP layer, embedded within a three-dimensional (3D) ECP matrix [15, 16, 22-25]. This approach leads to the formation of strong interactions – it was reported that the crosslinking agent (e.g., phytic acid) forms covalent bonds with hydrogen-terminated Si [26-30]. The hydrogel-derived architecture not only enhances electrical conductivity but also

promotes better connectivity between particles and accommodates volume expansion of Si during charge/discharge cycles, thereby improving mechanical stability and electrochemical performance [15, 16, 22, 25]. Consequently, hydrogel-derived anodes in LIB are expected to exhibit improved specific capacity and cycling stability during electrochemical testing. Nevertheless, the electrochemical performance of the hydrogel-derived anodes can be limited by the instability of ECP at wide potential windows. Indeed, ECP such as PANI, PPy, and PEDOT react with Li^+ within the potential range of 2.5–4 V, leading to material instability [31].

Although both physical blending and hydrogel-assisted synthesis are widely studied, a thorough and systematic comparison between these methods remains an area requiring deeper investigation. The literature contains only a few studies directly comparing anodes prepared by both methods. For instance, Li et al. [22] compared hydrogel-derived Si/PANI and Si/PPy with physically blended Si/PAA, and Liu et al. [15] compared hydrogel-derived Si/PPy with physically blended Si/PVDF, both highlighting the superior electrochemical performance of hydrogel-derived anodes. However, the lower electrochemical performance displayed by Si/PVDF and Si/PAA anodes in both studies is rather attributed to the absence of an electrically conductive additive, whereas the hydrogel-derived anodes benefited from an interconnected conductive network. Wu et al. [16] further explored this aspect by comparing the electrochemical performance of hydrogel-derived Si/PANI with a physically blended Si/pre-synthesized PANI. Consistent with previous findings, the hydrogel-derived anode demonstrated superior specific capacity and improved capacity retention. However, the poor electrochemical performance of the physically blended Si/PANI anode may not solely be due to the fabrication method but also to the intrinsic limitations of PANI, which is likely unsuitable as both a binder and a conductive additive. Thus, when comparing the physical blending with hydrogel-assisted synthesis, a key question remains: are the observed differences in electrochemical performance primarily due to the characteristics of the incorporated additives, or do they arise from the synthesis method itself?

To address this knowledge gap, this study conducted a systematic and comprehensive investigation comparing physical blending and hydrogel-assisted synthesis methods. Both types of anodes were prepared using four types of crystalline Si nanoparticles with different average particle sizes (6, 20, 55, and 100 nm), and their structural and electrochemical properties were systematically evaluated. To ensure that the resulting performance was not influenced by differences in the content or type of conductive additive or binder, anodes prepared by both methods were formulated with identical conductive additive (Super P) and

binder (PAA), with PAA also serving as a stabilizing agent for the Si nanoparticles. The electrochemical performance of hydrogel-derived composite anodes featuring a crosslinked PPy network was investigated in our previous study [25].

In this manuscript, the structural, morphological, and electrochemical properties of the anodes prepared using both methods were compared to establish structure–property relationships. These insights provided a deeper understanding of the internal processes occurring during battery cycling and the key differences between the two fabrication methods. We have proved that the electrochemical performance depends strongly on both Si particle size and preparation method. The direct comparison reveals multiple advantages and disadvantages of both methods that should be considered in further research when selecting a preparation method based on the intended application. Also, it was revealed that while small Si nanocrystals improve capacity retention in both systems, the benefit is substantially greater in hydrogel-derived anodes due to better dispersion, component connectivity, and mechanical support.

2 Experimental part

2.1 Materials

Si nanocrystals (SiNC) of four different sizes were used in this study. SiNC₁₀₀ with 100 nm average diameter (stock keeping unit NG04CO28095) and SiNC₅₅ with 55 nm average diameter (stock keeping unit NG04EO1804) were acquired from Nanografi. SiNC₆ with 6 nm average diameter and SiNC₂₀ with 20 nm average diameter were synthesized as a part of this study. The synthesis of SiNC₂₀ and SiNC₆ was carried out using diluted silane (1% in argon, Linde, Ar 5.0, SiH₄ 5.0, UN1954), hydrogen (H₂ 7.0, Linde, UN1049), argon (Ar, Ar 6.0, UN1006), and pure silane (SiH₄, UN2203). Carbon black Super P (40 nm average diameter) was kindly provided by Imerys S.A. Poly(acrylic acid) (PAA, M_w = 450,000), lithium hexafluorophosphate solution in ethylene carbonate and dimethyl carbonate (1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DMC = 50/50 (v/v), battery grade), and Li-metal foil (thickness: 0.6 mm, 99.9 %) were ordered from Merck group. Current collector copper foil (thickness: 25 μm, 99.8 %) was purchased from Thermo Fisher. All experiments related to electrode preparation were conducted in deionized water (DI) as an aqueous medium.

2.2 Materials Preparation

SiNC₂₀ and SiNC₆ were synthesized using a non-thermal plasma technique, yielding well-defined, hydrogen-terminated nanostructures. Detailed descriptions of the synthesis procedure are provided in our previous work [25]. Briefly, the plasma discharge was generated using an RF plasma source in a custom-built flow-through reactor. The nanocrystal size was controlled by adjusting the applied power and the specific ratios of the process gases.

Preparation of anode materials via physical blending: The anode materials were prepared via physical blending as follows. First, 60 mg SiNC (with an average particle size of 6, 20, 55, or 100 nm) was ground in a mortar for 10 minutes. Next, 20 mg of Super P were added and further ground for another 10 minutes. Subsequently, 20 mg of PAA binder was incorporated into the SiNC-Super P and blended for an additional 10 minutes. The resulting powder mixture was transferred into a glass vial, followed by the addition of DI water. To achieve uniform dispersion of the solid components, the suspension was stirred at 1100 rpm using a magnetic stirrer for 3 hours. The resulting ink was further homogenized by sonication (PS 3000, PowerSonic bath) for two 5-minute intervals. The homogenized ink was then cast onto a copper (Cu) foil current collector using a doctor blade to achieve a controlled film thickness. Finally, the coated anodes were dried in a vacuum oven at 60°C overnight. The prepared anodes were labeled as Super P/SiNC_x, where x corresponds to the average particle size (x = 6, 20, 55, or 100 nm). The anodes were not calendared to achieve a defined electrode density; instead, they were subjected solely to mechanical pressure.

Preparation of anode materials via hydrogel-assisted synthesis: The preparation method of anode materials via hydrogel-assisted synthesis is described in our previous work [25]. The prepared anodes were labeled as PPy/SiNC_x, where x is the size of the SiNC.

A schematic illustration of the anode preparation using physical blending and hydrogel-assisted synthesis is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the anode preparation using physical blending and hydrogel-assisted synthesis.

2.3 Characterization methods

The material structure and morphology were analyzed using transmission electron microscopy (TEM, EFTEM Jeol 2200 FS) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Mira3 LMH, Tescan, secondary electrons at 3 kV). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) analysis was conducted using Bruker XFlash 6|10 detector and software Esprit 2.1. The surface chemistry of SiNC was analyzed by Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) using a Nicolet iS50 ABX spectrometer. Raman spectra were collected using a Thermo Scientific DXR Raman microscope equipped with confocal microscope Olympus and with 633 nm line laser (power 6,8 mW). The spot size of the lasers was focused by 50× objective. The scattered light was analyzed by a spectrograph with holographic gratings (600 lines per mm), respectively, with spectrograph aperture of 50 μm pinhole. The acquisition time was 30 s with 30 repetitions.

The obtained composite anodes cast onto Cu foil were cut into circular pieces with a diameter of 1.5 cm, and each piece was weighed individually. The circular electrodes were then transferred into an argon-filled glovebox for the assembly of a half-coin cell LIB. The prepared electrodes served as the anode, while Li metal foil was used as the counter electrode. The electrolyte consisted of 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC/DMC.

The electrochemical performance of the assembled LIB was evaluated using galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCD) cycling, performed in the potential range of 0.05–1V vs. Li/Li⁺. The discharge corresponds to lithiation, while the charge corresponds to delithiation [32, 33]. The measurements were conducted using a battery tester (Neware BTS-4008-5V50mA) at 0.4 A/g (0.1C). The applied current was individually adjusted for each anode based on the active mass of Si. Additional electrochemical characterization included cyclic voltammetry (CV) using a

potentiostat (μ Autolab, Metrohm), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) in the fully discharged state (0.05 V) over a frequency range of 80 kHz to 0.03 Hz (Ivium CompactStat.h, Ivium Technology B. V.).

3 Results and discussion

3.1. Chemical and physical properties of SiNC and micro-structure of anodes

The chemical structure and solid-state properties of the four SiNC were described in our previous study, which focused on the hydrogel-assisted synthesis method [25]. The key characteristics are summarized in **Table S1**. Briefly, X-ray diffraction and Raman spectroscopy confirmed the crystalline Si nature of all the SiNC materials. An additional SiO_2 X-ray diffraction band was observed only in SiNC_{55} , suggesting a more pronounced oxidation state compared to other SiNC. Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy revealed the presence of oxidation and adventitious carbon on the Si surface, attributed to atmospheric exposure in all four cases. However, both commercial Si powders (SiNC_{100} and SiNC_{55}) exhibited a higher degree of surface oxidation, likely linked to their preparation process and subsequent handling by the supplier. Moreover, SiNC_{55} showed the highest proportion of Si^{4+} (35.6%) in Si corresponding to SiO_2 on the surface, which is consistent with the results from XRD analysis and suggests a more pronounced oxidation for this particular sample. The nitrogen physisorption technique revealed a significant increase in specific surface area with decreasing particle size. The average particle size, determined from TEM images (**Figure 2a, d, g, j**) using ImageJ [25], showed that lab-synthesized SiNC (SiNC_6 and SiNC_{20}) had a narrow size distribution (6 ± 1 nm and 20 ± 5 nm, respectively), whereas commercial SiNC (SiNC_{55} and SiNC_{100}) exhibited significantly broader distributions (55 ± 30 nm and 100 ± 45 nm, respectively).

The cross-sectional microstructures of all anodes fabricated by physical blending (Si/Super P) and by hydrogel-assisted synthesis (Si/PPy) were examined by SEM (**Figure 2**). The physically blended Super P/SiNC anodes are shown in **Figure 2b, e, h, k**, while the hydrogel-derived PPy/SiNC anodes are presented in **Figure 2c, f, i, l**. In the physically blended Super P/SiNC anodes, the interconnection between SiNC and Super P is maintained solely by the PAA binder, and no 3D conductive framework is formed. The particle dispersion is relatively poor, with distinct domains of aggregated Super P, particularly evident in Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ (**Figure 2b**), likely due to the hydrophobic nature of Super P, a behavior previously reported [2]. This effect

is less visible in Super P/SiNC₅₅ (**Figure 2e**), where the particle sizes of SiNC and Super P are more comparable. Aggregation of the lab-synthesized SiNC (SiNC₂₀ and SiNC₆) is also observed in Super P/SiNC₂₀ (**Figure 2h**) and Super P/SiNC₆ (**Figure 2k**), which can be attributed to their smaller size and lower surface oxidation, leading to weaker interactions with the PAA binder. As established in previous studies, PAA stabilizes Si nanoparticles through interactions with surface hydroxyl and carboxyl groups [23, 34]. Thus, the more oxidized surfaces of commercial SiNC₅₅ and SiNC₁₀₀ promote better dispersion compared to the lab-synthesized samples.

In contrast, the PPy/SiNC anodes prepared through the hydrogel-assisted method exhibit a uniform incorporation of both SiNC and Super P within a 3D crosslinked PPy network. This structure enhances particle interconnection and generally results in more homogeneous dispersion than in the physically blended anodes. The only exception is PPy/SiNC₆ (**Figure 2l**), where the quantum-dot-sized SiNC₆ tend to form small clusters embedded within the PPy matrix, likely due to their very high surface energy. The improved dispersion of Super P in PPy/SiNC is attributed to its interaction with the PPy network, which may partially coat the Super P and mitigate its hydrophobic aggregation.

Figure 2: TEM images of a) SiNC₁₀₀, d) SiNC₅₅, g) SiNC₂₀, and j) SiNC₆. SEM images of anodes prepared through hydrogel-assisted synthesis: b) PPy/SiNC₁₀₀, e) PPy/SiNC₅₅, h) PPy/SiNC₂₀, and k) PPy/SiNC₆. SEM images of anodes prepared by physical blending: c) Super P /SiNC₁₀₀, f) Super P/SiNC₅₅, i) Super P/SiNC₂₀, and l) Super P/SiNC₆. Dashed red circles highlight the domains of aggregated Super P.

The chemical composition of the cross-sections of the physically blended anodes was examined using SEM-EDX (**Table S2 and Figure S1**), confirming the presence of Si, C, and O. Cu originating from the current collector was also detected but was not further considered. Notably, the O fraction increases systematically with decreasing SiNC particle size. This trend does not mirror the XPS results obtained on the pristine SiNC powders (**Table S1**), where the commercial SiNC₁₀₀ and SiNC₅₅ exhibited nearly twice the O content (~33%) compared with the lab-synthesized SiNC₂₀ and SiNC₆ (~15%). The difference arises because SEM-EDX probes the composite electrode, including SiNC, binder, and Super P, whereas XPS reflects only the initial surface chemistry of the isolated SiNC powders.

SEM-EDX analysis of electrode cross-sections (**Table S2**) shows that the O fraction increases systematically in the anodes as SiNC size decreases. This trend can be attributed to several factors: (i) the higher surface-to-volume ratio of smaller SiNC, which promotes surface oxidation and hydroxylation during air exposure and aqueous slurry processing; (ii) stronger adsorption of the O-rich PAA binder and enhanced retention of water at particle–binder interfaces within the composite; and (iii) a relative decrease in the detected C fraction (from Super P and binder), which increases the apparent proportion of O in the EDX signal. Together, these effects explain the monotonic increase in O fraction from Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ to Super P/SiNC₆. Overall, the small, initially less-oxidized lab-synthesized SiNC (SiNC₆ and SiNC₂₀) appear more susceptible to oxidation under aqueous processing, whereas the commercial SiNC (SiNC₅₅ and SiNC₁₀₀), which already possess thicker native oxide layers, are less reactive.

To evaluate whether the increase in O content originates from surface oxidation, the surface termination of the largest and smallest SiNC (SiNC₁₀₀ and SiNC₆) was studied. Three forms of each SiNC material were analyzed by FTIR: the pristine SiNC powder, SiNC mixed only in an aqueous medium, and SiNC terminated with PAA in the aqueous medium (**Figure S2**). All spectra exhibit absorption bands of SiNC-based materials, in Si–H stretching modes (2246, 2191, 2095, 980, 902, 857, and 600–700 cm⁻¹), Si–OH stretches (3201 and 1625 cm⁻¹), and Si–O–Si modes (1045 and 793 cm⁻¹) [25, 30]. In PAA-terminated SiNC, the band at 1709 cm⁻¹ corresponds to PAA carbonyl groups, and the band near 1450 cm⁻¹ is assigned to C–H stretching [35]. The additional bands at 1206 and 1123 cm⁻¹ in SiNC₁₀₀ likely arise from carbonaceous [36] or SiO₂-related impurities [37–39]. The most notable difference between SiNC₁₀₀ and SiNC₆ appears in the 800–950 cm⁻¹ region. Pristine SiNC₆ exhibits only two bands associated with Si–H₃ or Si–H₂ modes [25, 30]. After mixing in water or after PAA termination, two new bands emerge at 833 and 876 cm⁻¹, both indicative of surface oxidation [30]. In

contrast, SiNC₁₀₀ already shows two bands at 842 and 876 cm⁻¹ prior to any treatment, consistent with a pre-existing oxide layer. Following aqueous or PAA termination, these band positions remain essentially unchanged, suggesting no substantial additional oxidation. These FTIR results support the SEM–EDX observations, namely, smaller SiNC undergo pronounced oxidation during aqueous processing, whereas the larger commercial SiNC, already oxidized in their pristine state, show limited reactivity. A similar phenomenon, where the Si surface oxide passivates the material and partially protects it from further oxidation in aqueous media, has been previously reported [40, 41].

Comparison of the physically blended Super P/SiNC anodes with the hydrogel-derived PPy/SiNC materials (SEM–EDX data in **Table S2**) reveals two key differences. First, the hydrogel-derived anodes contain additional elements—namely, N from PPy, S from APS, and P from PhA, confirming successful incorporation of the hydrogel components. Second, although the O fraction still increases with decreasing SiNC size, the overall O content is higher in hydrogel-derived anodes than in physically blended anodes. This increase likely arises from additional O-containing species introduced during the PhA-mediated hydrogel formation and the oxidative polymerization process.

3.2. Performance-related characteristics of prepared anodes

To evaluate the influence of structural and morphological differences between the anodes prepared via physical blending and hydrogel-assisted methods, half-coin-cell LIB were assembled and tested. GCD cycling was performed up to 500 cycles at a current density of 0.4 A/g within a potential window of 0.05–1 V.

The GCD cycling performance of the Super P/SiNC anodes is shown in **Figure 3a**, with a detailed view of the first 100 cycles in **Figure 3b**. The initial specific capacity increases with increasing SiNC particle size (**Figure S3a**), a trend also observed for PPy/SiNC anodes [25] (**Figure S3b**). Among the Super P/SiNC anodes, Super P/SiNC₁₀₀, containing the largest SiNC with the lowest specific surface area (11.4 m²/g), exhibits the highest initial charge and discharge capacities (2294 and 2581 mAh/g, respectively). In contrast, Super P/SiNC₆, containing the smallest SiNC (6 nm) with the highest specific surface area (509.4 m²/g), shows the lowest initial capacities (1100 and 1897 mAh/g). This behavior can be attributed to several interconnected factors. As mentioned above, SEM-EDX analysis of the electrode cross-sections (**Table 1**) showed that electrodes containing the smaller lab-synthesized SiNC (SiNC₆ and SiNC₂₀) exhibit the highest O fractions (21.6% and 12.9%, respectively). The elevated O

content in these electrodes arises from the higher specific surface area of the smaller SiNC and their greater susceptibility to surface oxidation during aqueous slurry-based electrode preparation. Surface oxidation reduces specific capacity through irreversible reactions of SiO₂ with Li⁺, forming lithium silicates or oxides during the first cycle [42]. In addition, the smaller particle size can hinder uniform binding with PAA and dispersion with Super P, potentially causing local aggregation, reduced electronic connectivity, and uneven Li⁺ diffusion. In contrast, commercial SiNC (SiNC₅₅ and SiNC₁₀₀) already have pre-existing surface oxidation (~33% O by XPS, **Table S1**), which partially protects them from further oxidation [40, 41], resulting in higher initial capacities and coulombic efficiency (CE). For example, Super P/SiNC₆, with the highest O fraction in the electrode cross-section (21.6%) and the highest specific surface area, exhibits the lowest initial CE (58%), while Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ shows the highest initial CE (89%). In subsequent cycles, the CE of all anodes rapidly stabilizes at ~100% (**Figure S3c and d**). This behavior is consistent with previous reports showing that smaller Si nanoparticles, owing to their high specific surface area, promote extensive SEI formation during the initial cycle, resulting in pronounced irreversible capacity losses [43-45].

Figure S4 and **Figure S5** compare the GCD cycling performance of physically blended Super P/SiNC with hydrogel-derived PPy/SiNC anodes over 500 cycles. Super P/SiNC anodes initially exhibit higher charge capacities but lower discharge capacities compared to PPy/SiNC, resulting in superior initial CE (**Figure S3c**). The slightly lower initial CE of PPy/SiNC (**Figure S3c**) is attributed to the 3D interconnected PPy network, which increases porosity and facilitates electrolyte penetration, enhancing initial SEI formation and Li⁺ consumption [46, 47]. During initial cycles, Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ maintains higher capacity for up to 250 cycles, Super P/SiNC₅₅ and Super P/SiNC₆ for up to 120 cycles, and Super P/SiNC₂₀ for up to 40 cycles, reflecting better initial lithiation kinetics. However, with prolonged cycling, PPy/SiNC anodes outperform Super P/SiNC counterparts in both specific capacity and cycling stability, except for PPy/SiNC₁₀₀, which exhibits performance comparable to Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ after approximately 250 cycles. This convergence in electrochemical behavior suggests that, for SiNC₁₀₀, the large particle size dominates the cycling response, thereby diminishing the impact of the anode preparation method. The increased susceptibility of large Si particles to mechanical cracking during repeated lithiation/delithiation likely overrides the potential benefits introduced by the PPy-based architecture, as larger Si particles are inherently more prone to fracture [44, 48-50].

At the 500th cycle, specific capacities of Super P/SiNC anodes are low and comparable: 119 mAh/g (SiNC₁₀₀), 63 mAh/g (SiNC₅₅), 72 mAh/g (SiNC₂₀), and 174 mAh/g (SiNC₆). In

contrast, PPy/SiNC anodes maintain higher capacities, increasing with decreasing SiNC size: 77 mAh/g (SiNC₁₀₀), 278 mAh/g (SiNC₅₅), 331 mAh/g (SiNC₂₀), and 434 mAh/g (SiNC₆). Capacity fading is attributed to Si degradation from volume expansion, unstable SEI formation, and gradual loss of electrical connectivity [52, 53]. The vastly superior cycling stability of PPy/SiNC highlights the key role of the 3D interconnected PPy network in enhancing mechanical integrity. The incorporation of large SiNC₁₀₀ particles may hinder the formation of a robust 3D PPy network, explaining the lower performance of PPy/SiNC₁₀₀ compared to Super P/SiNC₁₀₀.

Differences in capacity retention during GCD cycling (**Figure 3c–d**) further illustrate the particle-size dependence of PPy/SiNC anodes, with retention improving as particle size decreases, whereas Super P/SiNC retention remains largely unchanged for SiNC₁₀₀, SiNC₅₅, and SiNC₂₀, with a noticeable increase only for SiNC₆. Notably, for the smallest SiNC particles (6 nm), which show the best cycling stability for both methods, PPy/SiNC₆ clearly outperforms Super P/SiNC₆ over long-term cycling. Although both retain ~80% of their capacity after 100 cycles, PPy/SiNC₆ maintains 44% after 500 cycles, compared to only 16% for Super P/SiNC₆, demonstrating the beneficial role of the 3D interconnected PPy network in combination with small SiNC particles [25].

Figure 3e–f shows GCD profiles at 0.4, 0.7, 1.8, and 3.6 A/g for representative anodes. Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ and Super P/SiNC₂₀ are compared with PPy/SiNC₁₀₀ and PPy/SiNC₂₀, respectively. Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ demonstrates stable charge capacities from ~2081 to 611 mAh/g with good reversibility at lower currents. PPy/SiNC₁₀₀ shows a higher initial charge capacity (2698 mAh/g at 0.4 A/g) but drops sharply at higher currents. Super P/SiNC₂₀, with smaller SiNC, exhibits lower capacity, stability, and reversibility than PPy/SiNC₂₀ across all current densities, highlighting the advantage of integrating small SiNC within the 3D PPy network for improved anode performance.

Figure 3: GCD cycling in the potential window of 0.05–1 V at a current density of 0.4 A/g for a) Super P/SiNC anodes over 500 cycles and b) a zoomed-in view of the first 100 cycles. c) Capacity retention after 100 cycles and initial specific capacity (measured in the 2nd cycle) of Super P/SiNC. d) Comparison of capacity retention after 100 and 500 cycles for all PPy/SiNC and Super P/SiNC anodes. Specific capacity at various current densities for PPy/SiNC and Super P/SiNC anodes containing e) SiNC₁₀₀ and f) SiNC₂₀.

To investigate the evolution of electrochemical processes during cycling, differential capacity (dQ/dV) plots were analyzed. **Figure S6** depicts the 1st to 500th cycles of all physically blended anodes. The curves reveal pronounced differences in peak intensity, peak position, and overall shape. Consistent with previous reports, the plots display characteristic lithiation and delithiation features of Si (namely, two lithiation peaks at 0.18–0.25 V and 0.05–0.10 V corresponding to the conversion of Si to a-Li_xSi and subsequently to Li₁₅Si₄ [56, 57], and two delithiation peaks at approximately 0.25–0.32 V and 0.44–0.48 V associated with the reverse transitions to a-Si [56]). All physically blended electrodes exhibit these characteristic signatures. Interestingly, Super P/SiNC₆ shows an additional strong peak at ~0.46 V, while Super P/SiNC₂₀ exhibits a weaker feature at the same position during early cycles. To our knowledge, such a feature has not been widely reported in differential capacity plots for Si-based anodes; however, a similar peak has been observed in CV and attributed to partial reduction of the native SiO₂ layer on the Si surface [58, 59]. This assignment is consistent with the enhanced surface oxidation detected in SiNC₆ and SiNC₂₀ by SEM-EDX after anode fabrication.

To compare changes in electrochemical behavior between physically blended anodes Super P/SiNC and hydrogel-derived anodes PPy/SiNC, the 1st and 10th cycles of all anodes were examined (**Figure S7** and **Figure S8**). The comparison focused on relative peak intensities, shifts in peak positions, and changes in peak symmetry. Several trends emerge from this comparison. First, SiNC₁₀₀ exhibits superior electrochemical features in the physically blended anode, showing higher peak intensities and lithiation peaks at slightly higher potentials, which suggest improved lithiation kinetics and enhanced Li⁺ diffusivity [62]; SiNC₅₅ follows a similar trend. In contrast, SiNC₂₀ and SiNC₆ perform notably better in hydrogel-based anodes, with SiNC₆ displaying the most pronounced improvement. This indicates that the hydrogel-derived PPy network is more compatible with smaller SiNC, likely enhancing particle stabilization and mitigating degradation. Secondly, SiNC₅₅ shows an additional peak at ~1.24 V during the first cycle in the hydrogel-derived anode. Similar peaks have been associated with SiO₂ reduction in previous studies [63–65]. Although both anodes contain the same SiNC₅₅, this peak is absent in the physically blended Super P/SiNC₅₅ anode. The difference can likely be attributed to the hydrogel preparation, which incorporates PhA and PPy. These components can interact with the SiO₂ surface of the SiNC₅₅, enhancing its electrochemical activity and making the reduction peak observable in CV. In contrast, the physically blended anode lacks these chemical modifications, so the corresponding peak is not detected. Finally, an additional peak at ~0.46 V is observed in Super P/SiNC₆ and, more weakly, in Super P/SiNC₂₀, but is absent in the 10th-

cycle differential plots of the hydrogel-derived anodes. Since no direct quantification of surface oxidation is available, this difference is interpreted as an indirect effect of the anode preparation method on the electrochemical behavior of surface oxide species. The presence of this feature only in physically blended anodes may indicate differences in the chemical environment or accessibility of Si–O–related species, whereas the hydrogel-assisted synthesis, through the formation of a crosslinked PPy network and interactions involving PhA, may alter the electrochemical signature of these species. Such interfacial modifications could suppress or mask this feature in hydrogel-derived anodes, consistent with their improved structural integrity and cycling stability [30].

To further evaluate structural and morphological changes during cycling, Raman spectroscopy and SEM were conducted before and after 500 GCD cycles. Raman spectra of pristine anodes (**Figure S9**) exhibit the characteristic peak for crystalline Si at approximately 517 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the first-order phonon vibration mode of the Si lattice [25]. In addition, the broad D and G bands, centered around 1350 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} , respectively, are attributed to the carbonaceous Super P additive. These bands represent disordered carbon and graphitic-like structures, respectively, and their presence reflects the structural properties of the conductive additive in the anode [66]. After 500 cycles, the sharp Si peak at 517 cm^{-1} is significantly diminished, while a very weak band appears around 480 cm^{-1} [61, 62], indicating the transition of Si from a crystalline to an amorphous state during lithiation and delithiation [45]. The fraction of amorphous Si after cycling is higher for the hydrogel-derived PPy/SiNC₁₀₀ anode [25] compared to Super P/SiNC₁₀₀. The large background caused by the carbonaceous matrix and SEI residues does not allow for a direct comparison of the low-intensity amorphous-Si signals stemming from smaller SiNC. The SEM images of the anode samples before and after cycling (**Figure S10**) suggest structural changes, which are attributed to the merging of Si nanoparticles into a bulk-like phase, likely caused by mechanical stresses from volume expansion during cycling. This transformation reduces the available surface area for Li⁺ insertion/extraction, and leads to capacity loss and performance degradation. While SEM does not directly reveal the SEI layer, its growth is inferred from the increase in impedance and capacity fade, both of which hinder Li⁺ diffusion. The SEI layer likely contributes to the observed morphological changes, including the formation of a bulk-like phase and accumulation of residual electrolyte deposits in the pores, which can block active sites and reduce overall efficiency. SEM analysis of physically blended Super P/SiNC indicates aging behavior similar to that observed in the post-mortem analysis of hydrogel-derived anodes [25].

To further investigate the electrochemical redox processes, CV measurements were performed on a coin-type half-cell LIB with Super P/SiNC anodes within a potential window of 0.05–1 V at a scan rate of 0.1 mV/s (**Figure 4**). **Figures 4a-d** show the CV curves for 10 cycles and normalized to the mass of Si, while **Figures 4e-f** compare the 1st and 10th cycles. In the 1st cycle, all anodes show a broad reduction peak in the range of 0.35 – 0.70 V, which disappears in subsequent cycles. This feature is attributed to irreversible electrolyte decomposition and SEI layer formation on the SiNC surface [69]. Notably, Super P/SiNC₅₅ shows an additional weak reduction peak at 0.85 V during the first cycle, which is also observed in the corresponding dQ/dV plots at ~0.74 V (**Figure S8d**). This peak is commonly associated with the irreversible reduction of SiO₂ species in contact with Li⁺, consistent with the higher SiO₂ content of SiNC₅₅ [70, 71]. Its disappearance upon further cycling confirms its irreversible nature. As cycling proceeds, new peaks emerge, suggesting ongoing electrochemical processes [59], and gradual anode activation linked to the amorphization of crystalline Si [72].

All half-cell LIB display two cathodic peaks around 0.2 V and 0.05 V, corresponding to the transformation of the crystalline Si into an amorphous α -Li_xSi phase, followed by crystallization to Li₁₅Si₄ [56]. In agreement with the dQ/dV analysis, the CV curves of Super P/SiNC₆ show an additional peak at 0.4 V, which has been attributed to the partial reduction of the native oxide layer on the Si surface [58, 59]. This feature is not clearly visible in the CV curves of Super P/SiNC₂₀, reflecting the different sensitivities of CV and dQ/dV techniques, with dQ/dV analysis being more sensitive to subtle electrochemical features [73]. On the anodic branch, two oxidation peaks at 0.35 V and 0.5 V are observed, corresponding to the delithiation of amorphous α -Li_xSi and the Li extraction from Si, respectively [56, 59].

A direct comparison between Super P/SiNC and PPy/SiNC anodes (**Figure S11**) reveals that Super P/SiNC anodes show higher CV peak intensities after 10 cycles, indicating improved electrochemical activity and more effective utilization of the active material, potentially due to increased electrolyte accessibility [74]. Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ shows continuous activation over the first 10 cycles, whereas PPy/SiNC₁₀₀ exhibits a decline after five cycles, likely related to partial loss of electrochemically active SiNC during cycling [75]. When comparing Super P/SiNC₅₅ and PPy/SiNC₅₅ (**Figure S11b**), the irreversible SiO₂-related reduction peak at 0.85 V is less pronounced in Super P/SiNC₅₅. This difference may be attributed to the acidic environment and chemical interactions occurring during PPy hydrogel formation, which can modify the surface chemistry and electrochemical accessibility of oxide-related species on SiNC₅₅, thereby altering their CV signature [26-29], as discussed above.

Overall, the combined GCD, CV, and dQ/dV results indicate that small SiNC benefit most from hydrogel-assisted anode preparation. The 3D PPy network stabilizes the SiNC particles and promotes diffusion-limited lithiation, which is consistent with the improved long-term cycling performance of PPy/SiNC anodes. In contrast, physically blended Super P/SiNC₂₀ exhibits a higher capacitive contribution, reflecting more exposed SiNC surfaces but comparatively lower cycling stability over extended cycles.

Figure 4: CV measurements at a scan rate 0.1 mV/s for a) Super P/SiNC₁₀₀, b) Super P/SiNC₅₅, c) Super P/SiNC₂₀, and d) Super P/SiNC₆. Comparative CV curves of all anodes at 0.1 mV/s e) in the 1st cycle and f) in the 10th cycle.

To investigate the interfacial processes at the anode-electrolyte interface, EIS measurements were performed on two representative anodes containing SiNC₁₀₀ and SiNC₆, which correspond to the largest and smallest Si nanoparticle sizes studied, respectively.

Nyquist plots over five cycles, measured in the discharged state, are shown in **Figure 5**. Equivalent circuit fitting (**Figure S12**) was used to extract key resistances: cell resistance (R_s), SEI formation resistance (R_{SEI}) with its constant phase element (CPE_{SEI}), charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) with constant phase element (CPE_{CT}), and Warburg impedance (W) [25, 79–81]. Analysis of the EIS data (**Figure 5**) reveals consistently low and stable R_s values (4–3 Ω), reflecting a uniform battery setup [81]. R_{SEI} is the highest in the 1st cycle for both anodes, corresponding to initial SEI formation, and decreases in subsequent cycles as the SEI stabilizes. Initial R_{SEI} values are 61 Ω for Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ and 65 Ω for Super P/SiNC₆. The slightly higher value for Super P/SiNC₆ may reflect its smaller particle size, higher specific surface area, and greater surface reactivity, which promote more extensive SEI formation. However, the similarity of R_{SEI} values also suggests that SiNC₆ aggregation partially mitigates surface area effects. Over subsequent cycles, R_{SEI} in Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ gradually increases, suggesting ongoing SEI evolution, while R_{SEI} in Super P/SiNC₆ remains stable, consistent with improved SEI stability. A similar trend is observed for R_{CT} : Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ exhibits relatively constant values around 20 Ω , whereas Super P/SiNC₆ starts with a higher R_{CT} of 34 Ω that rapidly decreases to 2–3 Ω in later cycles, consistent with enhanced electrical connectivity and improved material utilization. These trends correlate well with the GCD performance and initial CE discussed earlier.

To compare the initial interfacial behavior between physically blended and hydrogel-derived anodes, EIS data for Super P/SiNC were overlapped with previously reported PPy/SiNC [25] (**Figure S13**). While Super P/SiNC anodes maintain relatively stable R_{SEI} and low R_{CT} values, PPy/SiNC anodes exhibit higher initial R_{SEI} followed by a rapid decrease, suggesting more pronounced SEI formation in the hydrogel-derived anodes. This behavior is consistent with their lower initial CE. The slightly higher R_{CT} observed in PPy/SiNC may reflect the presence of the 3D hydrogel network, which, while stabilizing the SiNC and mitigating degradation, can partially limit ion and electron transport compared to physically blended anodes. Overall, these results highlight the combined influence of SiNC particle size and anode architecture on interfacial stability and charge-transfer kinetics.

Figure 5: EIS results - the left charts show the evolution of resistances (R_S , R_{SEI} , R_{CT}), while the right charts present Nyquist plots at the discharged state (data points) with fitting (solid line) to the equivalent circuit (**Figure S12**) for a) Super P/SiNC₁₀₀ and b) Super P/SiNC₆.

4 Conclusions

This manuscript presents a comparative study of Si-based anodes for LIB application prepared using two different methods, namely, physical blending for Super P/SiNC and hydrogel-assisted synthesis for PPy/SiNC, and evaluates the effect of the used SiNC. Both types of anodes were prepared using four types of SiNC with varying average particle sizes (6, 20, 55, and 100 nm) and different surface chemistries (extent of surface oxidation). The Super P/SiNC anodes consisted of SiNC, Super P as a conductivity enhancer, and PAA, which provided mechanical stability but had limited electrical conductivity. In contrast, the PPy/SiNC anodes comprised SiNC, Super P, and a 3D-crosslinked PPy network, which functioned as an electrically conductive binder. The SEM analysis of the microstructure of the anodes revealed improved dispersion of SiNC and Super P in PPy/SiNC anodes, where the fillers were uniformly incorporated within the 3D PPy dendritic network. Conversely, Super P/SiNC anodes exhibited noticeable aggregation of Super P and SiNC, particularly in the case of the smaller lab-synthesized SiNC (SiNC₂₀ and SiNC₆). SEM-EDX and FTIR analyses indicated more pronounced surface oxidation in small SiNC after anode preparation, whereas commercial SiNC with higher pre-existing oxidation appeared partially protected.

GCD cycling over 500 cycles (0.05–1V) showed that Super P/SiNC anodes delivered higher initial specific capacities than PPy/SiNC, but their long-term cycling stability was lower. In both Super P/SiNC and PPy/SiNC, capacity retention improves as particle size decreases, although the effect varies slightly between the two. In PPy/SiNC, smaller SiNC particles exhibit particularly superior capacity retention. These results highlight the key role of the 3D PPy network in stabilizing SiNC, enhancing mechanical integrity, and improving long-term cycling performance. CV analysis confirmed enhanced lithiation kinetics and material utilization in Super P/SiNC anodes, likely due to greater electrolyte accessibility and higher capacitive contributions, whereas EIS measurements highlighted that PPy/SiNC anodes benefit from a protective network that shields SiNC from rapid degradation, albeit at the cost of slightly higher interfacial resistances.

Overall, the study demonstrates a trade-off between initial performance and durability. Physical blending produces higher initial capacities and faster kinetics, but more rapid capacity fading occurs due to aggregation and surface instability. Hydrogel-assisted synthesis results in lower initial capacity but markedly improved long-term stability, making it preferable for extended cycling applications. The optimal choice of fabrication method should therefore consider both

the SiNC particle size and surface chemistry. These findings provide valuable guidance for the design of high-performance Si-based anodes for high-performance LIB.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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